

Ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions of some tetraalkylammonium, alkali metals and ammonium halides in isoamyl alcohol at 298.15 K by conductometric technique

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Abstract : Precise conductance measurements are reported for tetramethylammonium chloride (Me_4NCl), tetraethylammonium bromide (Et_4NBr), tetrapropylammonium bromide (Pr_4NBr), tetrabutylammonium bromide (Bu_4NBr), tetrabutylammonium iodide (Bu_4NI), lithium bromide (LiBr), sodium iodide (NaI) and ammonium bromide (NH_4Br) in isoamyl alcohol at 298.15 K. The conductance data have been analyzed by the Fuoss conductance-concentration equation in terms of the limiting molar conductance (Λ_0), the association constant (K_A) and the distance of the closest approach of ions (R). The results have been explained in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions.

Keywords : Ion-solvated interaction, ion-ion interaction, conductometry.

Extensive studies on electrical conductances¹⁻³ in various solvents have been performed in recent years to examine the nature and magnitude of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. Such solvent properties as the viscosity and the relative permittivity have also been taken into consideration which helps to determine the extent of ion association and the ion-solvent interactions⁴⁻⁹.

The importance of isoamyl alcohol in research field is implied from the fact that it has applications in high energy modern batteries and organic syntheses including the manufacture of cosmetics and pharmaceutical products as manifested from the physico-chemical studies^{10,11}. It is useful in gas chromatography. It can isolate high quality RNA¹² from even the hardest to isolate samples for immediate use in microarray application and also it is used in most DNA applications¹³.

In the present work an attempt has been made to ascertain the complete nature of ion-solvent and ion-ion interaction of some tetraalkylammonium, alkali metals and ammonium halides in this medium through the measurements of their conductances.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of the equivalent conductances, Λ against the respective concentration, c of the tetraalkylammonium, alkali metals and ammonium halides in pure isoamyl alcohol at 298.15 K are recorded in

Table 1. The conductance data is analyzed using the Fuoss conductance equation¹⁴. So with a given set of conductivity values (c_j , Λ_j , $j = 1, \dots, n$), three adjustable parameters, i.e. Λ_0 , K_A and R are derived from the Fuoss equation. Here, Λ_0 is the limiting equivalent conductance, K_A is the observed association constant and R is the association distance, i.e. the maximum centre to centre distance between the ions in the solvent separated ion-pairs. There is no precise method¹⁵ for determining the R value but in order to treat the data in our system, R value is assumed to be, $R = a + d$, where a is the sum of the crystallographic radii of the ions, which varies from 3 to 7 Å and d is the average distance corresponding to the side of a cell occupied by a solvent molecule. The distance, d is given by¹⁴,

$$d = 1.183 (M/\rho)^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight and ρ is the density of the solvent.

Thus, the Fuoss conductance equation may be represented as follows :

$$\Lambda = P[\Lambda_0(1 + R_x) + E_L] \quad (2)$$

$$P = 1 - \alpha(1 - \gamma) \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A C \gamma^2 f^2 \quad (4)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta k/2(1 + kR) \quad (5)$$

$$\beta = e^2/Dk_B T \quad (6)$$

Table 1. Concentration (*c*) and equivalent conductance (Λ) values of some tetraalkylammonium, alkali metals and ammonium halides in pure isoamyl alcohol at 298.15 K

$c \times 10^4$ (mol lit ⁻¹)	$\sqrt{c} \times 10^2$ (mol ^{1/2} lit ^{-1/2})	Λ (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)	$c \times 10^4$ (mol lit ⁻¹)	$\sqrt{c} \times 10^2$ (mol ^{1/2} lit ^{-1/2})	Λ (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)
	Me ₄ NCl			Et ₄ NBr	
0.6315	0.7947	8.71023	0.6085	0.7801	9.45327
1.2160	1.1027	8.26212	1.2970	1.1389	8.91008
2.0160	1.4199	7.50030	2.1500	1.4663	8.18239
2.7370	1.6544	7.24320	2.9180	1.7082	7.09109
3.3880	1.8407	6.21376	3.6130	1.9008	6.73333
3.9810	1.9952	5.76115	4.2450	2.0603	6.06247
4.5210	1.1263	5.45242	4.8220	2.1959	5.57859
5.0170	1.2399	4.55224	5.3500	2.3130	5.00104
5.4730	2.3394	4.25726	5.8370	2.4159	4.64313
5.8940	2.4278	3.56205	6.2860	2.5072	3.73204
6.2840	2.5068	3.11346	6.5660	2.5624	3.26156
6.5280	2.5549	2.88000			
	Pr ₄ NBr			Bu ₄ NBr	
0.6008	0.7751	9.36252	0.5827	0.7633	8.94225
1.1570	1.0756	8.86109	1.2420	1.1145	8.00013
2.1540	1.4677	7.98514	2.0590	1.4349	7.55211
3.0230	1.7387	7.35312	2.7950	1.6718	7.27312
3.7870	1.9460	6.82222	3.4600	1.8601	6.67020
4.4630	2.1126	6.44106	4.0650	2.0162	6.27109
5.0660	2.2508	6.11923	4.6180	2.1489	6.14333
5.6070	2.3679	5.68402	5.1240	2.2636	5.36002
6.0960	2.4690	5.36165	5.5900	2.3643	5.00894
6.5390	2.5571	4.55232	6.0200	2.4536	4.88372
			6.2890	2.5078	4.45111
			6.5440	2.5581	3.71099
	Bu ₄ NI			LiBr	
0.6204	0.7877	9.91227	0.5833	0.7637	9.81301
1.1950	1.0932	8.78661	1.3930	1.1803	9.37430
1.7280	1.3145	8.10185	2.0150	1.4190	8.78412
2.6880	1.6395	7.45444	2.5940	1.6110	8.58107
3.5280	1.8783	6.91543	3.1350	1.7710	8.11111
4.2690	2.0662	6.27109	3.6410	1.9080	8.06258
4.9290	2.2201	5.82268	4.1150	2.0290	7.27536
5.5180	2.3490	5.61798	4.5600	2.1350	7.09289
6.0490	2.4595	5.20000	4.9790	2.2310	6.74004
6.5290	2.5552	4.55195	5.3740	2.3180	6.43841
			5.7480	2.3970	6.29784
			6.1010	2.4700	6.00498
			6.4350	2.5370	5.69777

Table-1 (contd.)

	NaI			NH ₄ Br	
0.6046	0.7776	8.18007	0.5888	0.7673	6.97670
1.1640	1.0789	7.88587	1.4070	1.1862	6.60098
2.1680	1.4724	7.62870	2.0350	1.4270	6.14251
3.0430	1.7444	6.97001	2.6190	1.6180	5.99465
3.8110	1.9522	6.52871	3.1650	1.7790	5.62401
4.4910	2.1192	6.29666	3.6750	1.9170	5.38776
5.0980	2.2579	5.82581	4.1540	2.0381	5.15166
5.6430	2.3755	5.67074	4.6040	2.1457	4.97394
6.1350	2.4769	5.54197	5.0270	2.2421	4.81400
6.5800	2.5652	5.15519	5.4260	2.3294	4.75488
			5.8030	2.4089	4.63553
			6.1590	2.4817	4.56243
			6.4970	2.5489	4.47899

$$K_A = K_R / (1 - \alpha) = K_R (1 + K_s) \quad (7)$$

where, Λ is the equivalent conductance at a concentration c (mol lit⁻¹), R_x is the relaxation field effect, E_L is the electrophoretic countercurrent, k^{-1} is the radius of the ion atmosphere, D is the relative permittivity of the solvent, e is the electron charge, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, γ is the fraction of solute present as unpaired ion, f is the activity coefficient, T is the absolute temperature and β is twice the Bjerrum distance.

The computations are performed on a computer using the program suggested by Fuoss. The initial Λ_0 values for the iteration procedure are obtained from Shedlovsky extrapolation of the data^{3,16,17}. Now, we input for the program, the no. of data, n , followed by D , η , initial Λ_0 value, T , ρ , M.W. of pure solvent along with c_j , Λ_j values where $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and an instruction to cover preselected range of R values.

In practice, calculations are performed by finding the values of Λ_0 and α which minimize the standard deviation, σ , whereby

$$\sigma = \Sigma [\Lambda_j (\text{calc.}) - \Lambda_j (\text{obs.})]^2 / (n - 2) \quad (8)$$

for a sequence of R values and then plotting $\sigma = 100\sigma / \Lambda_0$ against R , the best-fit R corresponds to the minimum of the σ versus R curve. So a approximate sum is made over a fairly wide range of R values using 0.1 increment to locate the minimum but no significant minima is found in the σ - R curves for all the salts studied here, thus R values is assumed to be $R = a + d$, with terms having usual significance¹⁴. Finally, the corresponding Λ_0 and K_A values are noted.

The Λ_0 , K_A and R values for the tetraalkylammonium, alkali metal and ammonium halides are thus reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Derived conductance parameters for the tetraalkylammonium, alkali metals and ammonium halides in pure isoamyl alcohol at 298.15 K

Salts	Λ_0 (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)	K_A (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	R (Å)	$\Lambda_0\eta$ (S cm ² mol ⁻¹ cP)	σ
Me ₄ NCl	15.92086	18774.39	10.94	0.609	0.94
Et ₄ NBr	15.49235	13351.93	11.61	0.593	0.89
Pr ₄ NBr	12.19570	4887.67	12.13	0.467	0.47
Bu ₄ NBr	12.15871	6430.30	12.55	0.465	0.63
Bu ₄ NI	13.63525	7569.45	12.77	0.522	0.36
LiBr	12.34061	3282.32	8.22	0.472	0.45
NaI	9.79606	2191.82	8.79	0.375	0.30
NH ₄ Br	8.45362	2569.44	9.09	0.324	0.15

The association constants, K_A recorded in Table 2 indicates that all the electrolytes are highly associated in this studied solvent. This is quite expected due to the low dielectric constant (14.7) of the solvent. The most outstanding feature is that the electrolytes containing smaller cations show almost considerable amount of association. Furthermore, the process of ionic association of these electrolytes does not exhibit the simple dependence upon ionic size as predicted by electrostatic theory.

Here, values of K_A decreases as the size of the cation increase with the exception of Bu_4N^+ ion. The same trend in association constants has also been observed for tetraalkylammonium salts in other pure alcohols^{18,19} such as methanol, ethanol, propanol, butanol and pentanol. The K_A values of the various electrolytes in this solvent follows the order :

However, in case of alkali metal and ammonium halides the trend is,

This may, however, be caused in case of tetraalkylammonium salts due to an increase in the ion-dipole interaction^{8,20}.

In case of Bu_4NI the value of K_A is greater than that of Bu_4NBr which is expected owing to the larger size of I^- compared to Br^- .

For NaI and $LiBr$, K_A value is greater in Li salt. This is due to smaller size of Li^+ compared to Na^+ resulting in higher solvation of Na^+ . But in case of ammonium and sodium halides, K_A of ammonium salt is greater due to larger size of I^- compared to Br^- .

The limiting equivalent conductances of the studied electrolytes is enhanced by the following order :

This can be explained in view of the variation of the Walden's product that has been reported in Table 2 which reflects the change of solvation²¹. The increase of the Walden product indicates the weak solvation of the ions in the pure solvent. This means higher is the limiting equivalent conductance value, lower is the solvation. The same pattern has also been manifested by some tetraalkylammonium salts in propanol and pentanol as reported earlier in previous papers²².

In case of Bu_4NI and Bu_4NBr there is exception due to presence of I^- ions and Br^- ions.

It has been already noted^{23,24} that Walden product of an ion or solute is inversely proportional to the effective radius of an ion or solute in a given solvent.

$$\Lambda_0\eta = 1/6\Lambda rT \quad (9)$$

Generally, Walden rule holds better for larger and not heavily solvated ions and hence having more or less the same effective radius in solvent.

Thus, the Walden's product increases in the order :

due to decreasing order of the crystallographic radii of the ions as :

Same can be observed and explained for the tetraalkylammonium halides as discussed earlier.

Experimental

Isoamyl alcohol (L.R.) procured from S.D. Fine-Chem Limited, Mumbai, was used after further purification. It was at first dried with $CaSO_4$ and then fractionally distilled²⁵. The purity of the solvent was checked by gas-liquid chromatography and was found to be better than 99.5%. The purified solvent had a density of 0.80685 g cm^{-3} and viscosity of 3.82782 cP at 298.15 K which was in good agreement with the literature values²⁶.

The salts Me_4NCl , Et_4NBr , Pr_4NBr , Bu_4NBr , Bu_4NI of A.R. grade were purified by dissolving in mixed alcohol medium and recrystallizing from solvent ether medium. After filtration, the salts were dried in oven for few hours. The salts $LiBr$, NaI , NH_4Br (A.R.) were dried at $\sim 80-100^\circ C$ in vacuum oven for 48 h before use²⁵.

The conductance measurements was carried out in a Systronic 306 conductivity bridge (accuracy $\pm 0.1\%$) using a dip-type immersion conductivity cell, CD-10 having cell constant $1.0 \pm 10\%$. Measurements were made in a thermostated water bath maintained at 298.15 K ± 0.01 K. Solutions were prepared by weight precise to $\pm 0.02\%$. Determination of cell constant was based on 0.01 (M) aqueous KCl solution. The entire conductance data was reported at 1 KHz and was found to be $\pm 0.3\%$ precise. The dielectric constant of isoamyl alcohol is 14.7 at 298.15 K. The concentration range of electrolytes was $\sim (0.6353 \text{ to } 6.353) \times 10^{-4}$ mol lit^{-1} ,²⁷. Molar conductances were calculated after the correction of solvent conductance $\sim 0.137 \times 10^{-6}$ mho cm^{-1} .

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References

1. M. N. Roy, D. Nandi and D. K. Hazra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 121.
2. B. Das and N. Saha, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2000, **45**, 2.
3. P. K. Mahuri and D. K. Hazra, *Z. Phy. Chem.*, 1995, **190**, 111.
4. A. K. Srivastava and R. S. Samant, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1994, **39**, 358.
5. H. Doe, H. Ohe, H. Matoba, A. Ichimura and T. Kitagawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1990, **63**, 2785.
6. S. Taniewska-Osinska, A. Piekarska, A. Bald and A. Szejgis, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **85**, 3709.
7. N. Islam, S. B. A. Zaidi and A. A. Ansari, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 309.
8. N. Papadopoulos, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1989, **67**, 1624.
9. M. S. K. Niazi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1988, **61**, 2165.
10. C. G. Janz and R. P. T. Tomkins, "Non Aqueous Electrolytes Handbook", Academic Press, New York, 1973, 2.
11. R. Jasinski, "High Energy Batteries", Plenum Press, New York, 1967.
12. J. Verga, E. Rinyu, E. Kevei, B. Toth and Z. Kozakiewicz, *Can. J. Microbiol/Rev. Can. Microbiol.*, 1998, **44**, 569.
13. "DNA Isolation Protocols", Biomolecule, Teaching Guide Supplement IVA, 6.
14. R. M. Fuoss, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 2427.
15. B. Per, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1977, **31**, 869.
16. D. S. Gill and M. S. Chauhan, *Z. Phy. Chem. NF*, 1984, **140**, 139.
17. G. C. Bag, N. M. Singh and N. R. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 294.
18. D. F. Evans and P. Gardam, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 3281.
19. Fernandez-Prini and J. E. Prue, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1965, **228**, 373.
20. R. L. Kay and D. F. Evans, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 4208.
21. U. G. K. Raju, B. Sethuraman and T. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 293.
22. D. F. Evans and P. Gardam, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 158.
23. C. G. R. Nair, R. L. Kumari and P. Indrasenan, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 525.
24. J. I. Bhat and P. Bindu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 788.
25. D. D. Perrin and W. L. F. Armarego, "Purification of Laboratory Chemicals", 3rd ed., Pergamon, Great Britain, 1988, 204.
26. A. K. Covington and T. Dickinson, "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", Plenum, New York, 1973.
27. M. S. Chauhan, K. Sharma and S. Chauhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1082.